

GraspOS SCOPE+i Resource:

Open Science assessment guide

Full resource

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Summary

This guide highlights Open Science (OS) outputs, activities and contributions that are relevant to consider in all types of OS aware research assessment (RA) processes.

Diversity of OS research outputs and activities is quite well understood but monitoring, assessing and rewarding OS is still challenging. Use of non-commercial databases OpenAlex, OpenAIRE Graph, and BIP!Services are recommendable despite the need for ongoing updates to their content and data accuracy regarding OS.

Many countries actively monitor and promote the implementation of OS principles and declarations. OS practices within organizations shape the daily research practices of individual researchers, placing researchers at the heart of the OS movement.

The impact of the OS is interesting. Verifying causality and correlation between interventions, outcomes and impacts is not easy and not everything can be measured. And maybe because of that and despite the guiding principles, ambitious goals and shared values, academic recognition and rewarding systems are still either missing or incomplete.

This guide can be used in all kinds of research evaluation processes and for all disciplines. The guide is aimed both for researchers and organizations.

Explore also

- Guide on promoting OS contributions in a narrative CV
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15525987>
- Guide on the diversity of OS contributions, roles and activities
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526089>

Look also publications of the YUFERING project

- Maria Pietilä, Katri Rintamäki, & Jouni Kekäle. (2023). YUFE Open Science Model and guidelines for researchers' evaluation (Versio 1). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10131115>
- Jouni Kekäle, Maria Pietilä, & Katri Rintamäki. (2024). Report on the accreditation pilot based in Open Science criteria (Versio 2). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640319>

Guide as part of SCOPE+i Resources and in relation to SCOPE Framework

The [SCOPE+i Resources](#) aim to facilitate the transition towards Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) with particular focus on contributions to OS. Being one out of 17 resources (guides, templates and checklists), this guide supports the structured organization of research assessment process and information from initial planning through to the publication of assessment protocols.

SCOPE+i Resources are aligned with the [SCOPE Framework](#), a five-stage model for evaluating responsibly. It is a practical step-by-step process designed to help research managers, or anyone

involved in conducting research evaluations, in planning new evaluations as well as checking existing evaluations. SCOPE is an acronym, where S stands for START with what you value, C for CONTEXT considerations, O for OPTIONS for evaluating, P for PROBE deeply, and E for EVALUATE your evaluation. This guide is most relevant for the stages S and C.

Figure 1. SCOPE Framework by INORMS (2023) (modified by highlighting the most relevant stages for this resource).

More about SCOPE Framework in International Network of Research Management Societies (INORMS) - Research Evaluation Group (2023). The SCOPE Framework. The University of Melbourne. Report. <https://doi.org/10.26188/21919527.v1>

All SCOPE+i Resources are brought together in the [GraspOS Infrastructure](#) (i), a simple, user-friendly interface (UI) where you can explore project results and save documents to learn and share with others.

Declarations and agreements

Open Science (OS) is a top research policy priority in Europe and globally. The values of OS are quality and integrity, collective benefit, equity and fairness, diversity and inclusiveness.

Responsibility in research assessment (RA) embraces a values-driven approach that aligns with an organization's mission and values, promoting clear, transparent, open and fair criteria in research assessment, ensuring non-discriminatory practices (Allen, L. et al., 2025).

Some important international statements

The [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#) (2021) has defined that "Open science is a set of principles and practices that aim to make scientific research from all fields accessible to everyone for the benefit of scientists and society as a whole. Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable."

For the member states UNESCO Recommendation means that:

- states are recommended to engage actively in removing the barriers for OS

- assessment of scientific contribution and career progression is rewarding good OS practices
- there is a need to change the current research culture to recognize researchers for sharing, collaborating and engaging with other researchers and society
- research assessment and career evaluation systems should be reviewed to align them with the principles of OS

UNESCO has also published the [Recommendation on Open Educational Resources](#) (2019) which emphasizes capacity building, developing supporting policies, ensuring quality and equality, promoting economic sustainability and fostering and facilitating international cooperation. Recommendation applies to all learning, teaching and research materials in any format and medium.

[The 2022 Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment \(ARRA\)](#) emphasizes the importance of developing and refining assessment criteria, tools, and processes in collaboration with both evaluators and those being evaluated. It highlights the need to recognize a wide range of research contributions extending beyond traditional journal articles and across different languages. It also stresses valuing practices that strengthen research quality, such as openness, transparency, inclusivity, peer review, and collaborative work. In addition, it calls for acknowledgment of diverse professional activities, including teaching, leadership, supervision, training, and mentoring, with consideration for the particular norms of each discipline.

ARRA is the result of international cooperation initiated by the European Commission. The implementation of the agreement is promoted by the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#). Signatory organizations agree to share how their organisation has started the process of reviewing or developing criteria, tools and processes in line with the core commitments and according to an Action Plan with defined milestones within one year of signing the agreement. Action plans are published in the [Zenodo](#) community. By the end of 2027 or within five years of signing the agreement organizations agree to regularly demonstrate progress on how they are fulfilling the core commitments.

[Plan S](#) requires that, from 2021, scientific publications that result from research funded by public grants must be published in compliant Open Access journals or platforms.

[Barcelona Declaration](#) (2024) has four commitments highlighting openness as default for all research information that is used and produced as well as support for services, systems, infrastructures and collective actions.

[OPUS project](#) is an EU-funded project developing a set of interventions for OS toward a system that incentivises and rewards researchers to take up practices of providing open access to research outputs, early and open sharing of research, participation in open peer-review, measures to ensure reproducibility of results, and involving all stakeholders in co-creation.

OA research outputs, activities and indicators are well identified

OS research outputs and activities are quite well identified. However, the differences in understanding of OS and all activities related to OS makes monitoring challenging. Rafols et al. (2024) mention that *“there is a danger that by focusing on what can be readily observed (e.g.*

publications) many other OS activities are overlooked (e.g. participation), with a potential narrowing of OS scope, streetlight effects, and deviation from the values of OS”.

The table below introduces topical systems that include or present OS contributions and indicators for both individual researchers and research institutions.

Table 1. Tools and sources of OS contributions and indicators.

Tool or source	OS activities, outputs and contributions
OpenAIRE Monitor	<p>OpenAIRE Monitor tracks research outputs, connects projects, and provides insights into impact and openness through advanced metrics and curated data.</p> <p>Entities for research products, publications, research data, research software, other research products, projects and unidentified projects.</p> <p>Inherited and inferred attributes for e.g. organizations, countries, funders, types of research outcomes, access rights, APCs, CC licenses, PIDs, repositories. Fields of science and SDGs under development.</p> <p>Constructed attributes for journal business models, journal APC business models, routes to OA, composite scores.</p>
OS-CAM (European Commission, 2017)	<p>Includes OS activities and possible evaluation criteria for research outputs, research process, service and leadership, research impact, teaching and supervision, professional experience.</p> <p>Can be used to develop evaluation systems that can be applied in various contexts: at individual level for the purpose of recruitment and promotion, at individual or group level in the evaluation of grant and fellowship applications or adapted to develop institutional funding allocation models or incentives focused on building open science capacity.</p>
PathOS OS Impact Indicator Handbook (Apartis et al., 2023)	<p>Covers OS from infrastructure to policies and practices: apc costs; availability of data repositories, preprint repositories and publication repositories; citizen science indicators; deposition of open metadata; evaluation of open science in research assessment; distribution of open access journal models; prevalence of open access publishing, national open science policies, open/fair data practices, open method practices, open peer review, open science funding policies, open science support and training, preprinting and replication studies; transformative publishing agreements.</p>
Openness profile. Synthesis of various open scholarship taxonomies (Jones & Murphy, 2021)	<p>The Openness Profile is a digital resource, a portfolio of a research contributor's outputs and activities, accessible in a single place. Academic and non-academic open scholarship activities become visible and more easily recognised.</p>

	<p>In Appendix C (p. 58 in the report by Jones & Murphy) a synthesis of various open scholarship taxonomies as well as the tools used in those activities is presented.</p> <p>List of activities: assessments, outreach, publication, writing, analysis, discovery, leadership, networking, academic standing, teaching and supervision, continuing professional development.</p>
<p>OPUS Researcher Assessment Framework (O'Neill, 2024)</p>	<p>The RAF covers the spectrum of researcher activities and offers researchers the possibility to be assessed on all relevant activities, rather than solely on the traditional metrics.</p> <p>Activities: research, education, leadership and valorisation.</p> <p>For the use of research performing organizations and research funding organizations to determine how to reward researchers for OS.</p>
<p>Hyrkkänen et al., 2023</p>	<p>Examples of different types of OS indicators identified in desktop research: lifelong learning, OA share (researchers), OA share (research entity), OA works/publications, open datasets and metadata, open software/code, open research methods, preregistrations, open peer review (as author or reviewer), open licences, open educational resources, use of open learning resources, open online courses, OS training, OS in the content of teaching, openness on contributorship, publication of co-author statements.</p>

Development of researcher level indicators is based on e.g. the [Metric Tide](#), the [Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics](#), and the [DORA declaration](#).

Understanding the pathway how research activities and outputs lead to outcomes and finally to impact is difficult. Verifying causality and correlation between interventions like policies, outcomes like research outputs e.g. publications and impact like cost-savings or economic growth is not easy. Also, lack of standards for measuring impact of OS are missing. Finally, everything is not measurable.

OpenAlex, OpenAIRE and BIP!Services

OS research outputs and activities are quite well identified but the knowledge base of commonly used information sources, databases and CRIS systems has not been developed to match all requirements of OS aware RA due to many reasons like lack of knowledge and resources for developing systems. Voluntary registration of other research outputs and activities other than “non-publications” is a problem.

Most databases offer possibilities to explore OA publications. Unfortunately, some databases are not able to register OA publications opened through self-archiving which is a challenge.

Table 2. shows that many OS activities are not indexed in [OpenAlex](#), [OpenAIRE](#) and [BIP!Services](#) making OS contributions of research/ers invisible. On the other hand, non-commercial and accessible databases are comprehensive e.g. in relation to a wide range of publication types and

their use is in line with the [Barcelona Declaration](#) (2024). Harmonization of the terms related to OS contributions e.g. with ORCID would be useful as ORCID is one source of information for the three databases.

Table 2. Support for representation of research entities and output types in global platforms and models (modified from the tables in Hyrkkänen et al. 2023, p. 107, 110, 113, 116). Please note that the table is based on information from the year 2023.

Entity type	OpenAlex	OpenAIRE	BIP!Services
Publications	Yes	Yes	Yes
Journal articles	Yes	Yes	Yes
Scientific publications beyond journal articles	Yes	Yes	Yes
Open access publications	Yes	Yes	Yes
Funding information	Yes	Yes	Yes
Persons	Yes	Yes	Yes
Research data	Yes	Yes	Yes
Datasets	Yes	Yes	Yes
Open research data	Yes	Yes	Yes
Organization	Yes	Yes	Yes
Software	No	Yes	Yes
Training, mentoring and supervision of PhD candidates	No	Yes	Yes
CVs	No	No	Yes
Peer review	No	No	Yes
Data models	Yes	Yes	No
Policy contributions	No	Yes	No
Projects	No	Yes	No
Activities	No	Yes	No
Open source software	No	Yes	No
Infrastructures	No	Yes	No
Leadership roles	Partially	Yes	No
Theories	No	No	No

Strategies	No	No	No
Exhibitions	No	No	No
Industry-academia cooperation	No	No	No
Methods	No	No	No
Protocols	No	No	No
Workflows	No	No	No
Algorithms	No	No	No
Skills and competencies	No	No	No
Teaching	No	Partially	No
Entrepreneurship	No	No	No
Science communication and interaction with society	No	No	No
Team science and collaboration	No	No	No
Skills, competence and merits	No	No	No
Knowledge valorization	No	No	No
Roles outside of academia	No	No	No
Diverse contributor roles (Data steward, software engineer, and data scientists)	No	No	Partially
Citizen science	No	No	No
Other open science elements (open-science related events, courses, projects)	No	No	No

Explore also

- Indicators guide 1: Responsible use of indicators. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526168>

OS monitoring

OS monitoring practices

Monitoring framework for OS requires a change in conventional monitoring practices. The scope should broaden from current focus on outputs such as publications towards the processes of connection that make science “open” – referring to usage, co-creation and dialogue, as well as towards outcomes, i.e. changes in practices and the longer-term impacts that reflect the values and normative commitments of OS. (Rafols et al (2024).

Rafols et al. (2024) propose that the OS monitoring efforts should shift towards:

- (i) systemic perspectives which consider the various actions related to OS, including
 - a. policies and outputs (e.g. datasets) but also
 - b. processes (e.g. participatory events),
 - c. outcomes (e.g. citizen interest in science) and
 - d. expected impacts (e.g. better scientific contributions to addressing societal problems);
- (ii) implementation of monitoring as reflexive learning (rather than accountability or benchmarking);
- (iii) mapping the directionality of the activities and the values associated with the choices in directions.

Examples of national OS monitoring systems

[French Open Science Monitor](#) (Baromètre Français de la Science Ouverte, BSO) aims to measure the evolution of OS in France using reliable, open and controlled data. The monitor is updated at the beginning of each year and the entire BSO data is made available as open data on the [MESR Open Data](#) portal and the source code is openly available on [github](#). Every French institution can implement its own localised [dashboard](#) based on the national system.

French [Open Science Monitoring Initiative](#) (OSMI) brings together institutions and individuals involved in monitoring open science. OSMI aims to encourage the adoption of open science monitoring principles and to promote their practical implementation like setting up their own monitoring tools.

[National Open Access Monitor Ireland](#) is a collaborative project by the National Open Research Forum (NORF), Irish Research eLibrary (IReL), and OpenAIRE. It aims to track Ireland's progress toward making all publicly funded research publications inclusively and sustainably open access by 2030, as outlined in the National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030. The Monitor provides valuable insights into Ireland's open science landscape and supports the shift toward a fully open access research ecosystem.

[Finnish OS monitoring](#) system is carried out every two years. The objective of the monitoring is to support the development of OS, support and verify the achievement of the commonly agreed principles and form an overall view of the state of openness in Finnish science and research.

UNESCO's [Draft Principles for Open Science Monitoring](#) for the countries who have adopted the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science is being updated. A draft of the [Open Science Monitoring Initiative](#) is also available. The aim of the draft is to create profound guidelines for monitoring not only OA of scholarly articles but also across all the pillars of OS and across all the stages of the scientific cycle. The upcoming monitoring system will be a combination of open qualitative and quantitative elements reflecting the values and principles of OS.

In the Netherlands a [project to develop a national OS monitor has started](#). The desired outcome of the project is a functional prototype of a dashboard that visualises both quantitative and qualitative data on research conducted at universities, universities of applied sciences, and other research institutions.

University of Bristol with [Open and Responsible Researcher Reward and Recognition Project \(OR4\)](#) has published a [Toolkit for recognizing and rewarding open research](#) (2024) which is designed to help universities and other research-performing organisations implement effective recognition and reward for open research through researcher assessment practices. The toolkit has two components providing practical guidance in nine actions areas.

Components of the toolkit:

1. [maturity framework and self-assessment tool](#) that institutions can use to assess their maturity in the implementation of relevant policies and procedures, to support internal discussion and planning, and to measure ongoing progress
2. [implementation guide](#) consisting of an introduction and sections linked to corresponding action areas in the maturity framework, providing detailed practical guidance to support assessment, planning and progress

Table 3. Action areas of the Recognising and rewarding open research toolkit - [Toolkit overview](#)

Strategy and leadership	1. Institutional commitment 2. Leadership 3. Strategy and planning
Implementation	4. Communication and engagement 5. Policy and procedure 6. Support, systems and processes 7. Guidance and training
Managing progress	8. Monitoring and evaluation 9. Research planning

(UK Reproducibility Network, 2024)

Adopting the FAIR principles advances OS

FAIR is an acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The FAIR principle is commonly used for research data management, but it is suitable for all research outputs including publications, data, software etc.

There are many levels of FAIR. The first step is to make all research outputs findable for both humans and machines. In order to achieve this goal permanent identifiers (PIDs) are the key point. An identifier is a label which gives a unique name to an entity: a person, place or thing. Examples of permanent identifiers are ORCID for researchers, DOI or URN for publications and ISBN for books. The role and development of PIDs, OS and FAIR principles go hand in hand.

Accessibility to research outputs varies depending on the type of output. For publications open access (OA) is quite established, and it increases the visibility, use and impact of publications.

Table 4. Open access publishing models.

Diamond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> articles published in journals which publish open access without charging APCs
Gold	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> article is freely and immediately available to anyone upon publication author pays Article Processing Charges, APCs
Bronze	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> articles of the journal are freely available on the publisher's website, but without an open access license
Green	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> article is published in a subscription-based journal and self-archived in an institutional repository depending on the publisher's terms for self-archiving the article may be freely available either immediately or after an embargo period
Hybrid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> article is published in a subscription-based journal, but which allows individual articles to be made freely accessible by paying an APC some publisher's terms and conditions can allow self-archiving also without an APC
Black	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> illegal OA articles shared in pirate sites

[Jisc Open policy finder](#) is a tool for searching open policies by publisher, journal or funder. List of [Jisc-approved transformative journals](#). Transformative journals (TJs) are subscription/hybrid journals that commit to transitioning to full open access.

For research data sets access can vary from closed to open. For open research data, options can be e.g.

- immediately open
- open after an embargo period
- open after registration
- open via an authorization procedure

Limited openness to data sets must be justified in many data repositories when saving metadata of research data, and also in grant applications. However, publishing the metadata of research data is always reasonable and it makes data findable. Also, careful citing - including in-text citations and reference in reference list - to research data in publications increases findability and use of research data. Lack of citing practices can even be one of the biggest challenges for FAIRdata.

Interoperability and reusability for research data sets are challenging to achieve completely. They are about licensing, using thesauruses and ontologies with PIDs, using open document formats like txt or csv, preparing thorough documentation etc. Eventually, making research data fully machine-readable and for the use of e.g. artificial intelligence.

Licenses give everyone from individual creators to large institutions a standardized way to grant the public permission to use their creative work under copyright law. From the reuser's perspective, the

presence of a license on a copyrighted work answers the question *What can I do with this work?* [Creative Commons](#) is one widely used licensing system.

Research outputs and researchers can be linked and connected with each other by citing and citations, making citations and cited networks which are crucial for e.g. systematic literature reviewing. Platforms like [ScienceOpen.com](#) enable research results to be immediately, open and citable with a PID like DOI.

[ORCID](#) is the international Open Researcher and Contributor ID. It provides a permanent and unique digital identifier for a researcher. ORCID ID is a series of numbers that will distinguish a researcher from other researchers. Registration is needed, and updates and visibility depend on the researcher's activity. Biographies, employment, education and qualifications, professional activities, funding and works can be added to ORCID, and it can be used to complement a researcher's CV. ORCID is free of charge.

Registration of works in ORCID makes possible to highlight and make visible a wide range of research outputs and activities including:

- Publications: book, book chapter, book review, dictionary entry, dissertation/thesis, edited book, encyclopedia entry, journal article, journal issue, magazine article, manual, newsletter article, newspaper article, online resource, preprint, report, research tool, review, supervised student publication, test, translation, website, working paper
- Conference: conference abstract, conference paper, conference poster
- Intellectual property: disclosure, license, patent, registered copyright, trademark
- Other: annotation, artistic performance, data management plan, data set, invention, lecture/speech, physical object, research technique, software, spin off company, standards and policy, technical standard

Many databases like OpenAlex, OpenAIRE and OpenCitations as well as some national solutions like Finnish Research.fi make use of ORCID making it a very important source of information for RA processes. Creating an ORCID account is voluntary but highly recommended. Keeping ORCID records updated also benefits research infrastructures by propagating open metadata and thereby enhancing institutional and national CRIS systems and funder grant platforms.

The [Openness Profile](#) was firstly termed in Knowledge Exchange as

"The mechanisms and approaches required to improve and incentivize the recording, evaluation and recognition of contributions to Open Scholarship practice, through the development of an 'Openness Profile'".

The GraspOS openness profile enables users to list OS outputs and activities, all accessible in one single location. These outputs may include contributions in non-academic journals and on platforms for societal, economic and policy audiences, practices like open peer review, training and mentoring, leadership roles, and, for reporting skills identified by the new ESCO Researchers Profile. [Read more about European multilingual classifications of skills, competences, qualifications and occupations.](#)

The [Research Activity Identifier \(RAiD\)](#). The RAiD service, developed originally by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC), is being implemented as an EOSC RAiD service, via the

[FAIRCORE4EOSC](#) project (Suominen, et al. 2024). The RAiD is a persistent identifier (PID) plus a metadata record for project information and a global registry dedicated to research projects (<https://raid.org>).

In the GraspOS project RAiD is adapted for the development of three assessment services: Assessment Portfolio, Assessment Registry, and Openness Profile. In addition, the BIP! Scholar service is planning to implement the Openness Profile.

Narrative CV is a flexible and adaptable tool for different disciplines and career stages. It can be used to highlight how a researcher has communicated ideas and research results, both written and verbally. In narrative CV a researcher can highlight how the OS and FAIR principles have been followed and implemented. [Royal Society Résumé for Researchers](#) is the most used template for OS narrative CV. It can be customized by organizations. OS can be integrated inside modules or - if preferred - OS can be an additional module. The narrative CV is not yet well adapted. Both evaluators and evaluand need training and support.

Monitoring and assessing OS

Pathway from OS activities and outputs to research outcomes and impact

Impact of OS can be studied as short-term impact and long-term impact. [Senior Consultant Lennart Stoy from Technopolis Group](#) presented in PathOS webinar on 11th March 2025 examples on how open and FAIR data and OA of publications leads to impact (Figures 2 and 3). More efforts are needed to create real incentives for real short- and long-term effects of OS like uptaking of research results by industry or SDG solutions.

Figure 2: Impact of Open and FAIR data (Stoy et al., 2025).

Figure 3: Impact of Gold and hybrid OA (Stoy et al., 2025).

Cole et al. (2024) have studied societal impact of OS. Their findings show that OS generates societal impact in terms of education and awareness, climate and environment, engagement, policy and governance, equity and empowerment, health, and trust and attitudes toward research. Findings also show that the evidence is presented primarily attributed to the impact of citizen science (CS). According to Dr Nicki Lisa Cole societal impact of OS increases efficiently with multistakeholder and CS research projects (a comment in PathOS webinar 28th Feb 2025, Cole & Apartis, 2025).

Alternative assessment criteria like altmetrics are a sign of valuing scientific outreach. Popularization of research, communication using many languages, acting as an expert in media and with relevant societal stakeholders, commercialization of research, collaboration with business – all these are examples how OS science can be fostered.

Academic impact refers to e.g. scientific citations. The question is, how openness of research outputs affects the academic impact of research. Klebel & Stavropoulos (2025) found that OA of publications, citizen science and FAIRdata can have a significant role on academic impact. This is something worth taking into account in research practices. At this point it is good to remind readers about responsible use of metrics in research assessment, especially when assessing individual researchers.

There are challenges and limitations in assessing the impact of OS - which should be understood differently from the “effect of openness on impact”. Verifying causality and correlation between interventions, outcomes and impacts is not easy and not everything can be measured. Also, there is a lack of standards for measuring OS impact and interpretation of OS indicators requires causal thinking according to Vincent Traag (2025).

Building and broadening new blocks for assessing scholarly impact and OS can help institutions to recognize and reward a wider variety of academic achievements and outcomes. Schmidt (2022) suggests new dimensions for broadening the definition of scholarly impact, namely the scale of

contributions' influence such as collaborations, mentoring and demonstrations of eminence, and new types of audiences such as audiences outside of disciplinary or academic peers.

Credit, merit and incentives for researchers

OS and normalizing open scholarship practices has proven challenging. What would be incentives for the attitudes towards OS and behaviour we would like to see? Is the best incentive just making OS easy and normative? Giving value to and credit of all relevant research activities and scientific outputs including high-quality FAIRdata, well-documented and reusable software, protocols and workflows, machine-readable summaries of findings, and teaching, outreach and engagement of societal actors is important.

Aubert Bonn and Pinxten (2021) highlight the difference between research success and career success. Research success is described with terms quality; valid and reproducible findings; collaboration; OS; innovation and negative findings; transparency, honesty and modesty. Career success is described with the terms quantity; exceptional findings; individual achievements; competitive; positive results and sensational.

Despite the guiding principles, ambitious goals and shared values, academic recognition and rewarding systems are still either missing or incomplete. According to Grattarola et al. (2024) there are gaps between OS activities and actual recognition systems, and according to the survey *“The most preferred type of reward was OS indicators in research evaluation and/or career progression processes”*. Lack of tangible incentives does not contribute to the development of OS.

Table 4. Terminology for OS credits and rewards (Grattola et al., 2024).

Table 2. Terminology for Open Science credits and rewards.

Category	Term
policies	OS indicators in research evaluation and/or career progression processes (e.g., considering open access publications and high-quality FAIR datasets when making decisions for research evaluation, promotion and tenure)
tangible rewards	funding/grants for OS activities
tangible rewards	awards/bonuses
tangible rewards	research visibility indicators
tangible rewards	authorship/contributorship
capacity building or support	capacity building for OS (e.g., training, raising awareness, provision of IT tools)
tangible rewards	acknowledgement/citation
policies	support through regulations and policy mandates
tangible rewards	collaboration (e.g., joint research, co-authorship)
intangible rewards	contribution to 'good' science, research quality and integrity
capacity building or support	OS certifications/badges
intangible rewards	science as a public good
tangible rewards	CRedit taxonomy
tangible rewards	financial contribution to reviewers of open access journals
tangible rewards	OS activities included in working hours
sanctions or penalties	punishment for 'closed' science
intangible rewards	research reputation
capacity building or support	championships/contests

For a researcher an incentive could be an award, bonus in addition to salary, badges in journals for sharing data and above all comprehensive, systematic and transparent examination of the wide range of work areas, merits and competences of an individual researcher in various assessment situations e.g. recruitment, tenure processes or promotion. For individual researchers the criteria for assessing OS must be carefully considered. For example, OA publishing depends on many things, many of which a researcher may not have the opportunity to influence. Instead, all kind of contribution and activities to support OS are worth incentives, for example

- working as a data steward
- sharing teaching material
- participating in OS communities and development projects
- funding received for OS
- participating in citizen science

Researchers need motivation, support and training and organizations possible pressure of some kind. Economic challenges need to be solved. More money is needed to develop free information sources, databases, CRIS systems, and research funders information systems. E.g. CRIS systems need to be developed so that a wide range of OS research outputs and activities can be recorded and reported. Making a CRIS form more flexible by adding space for researchers to describe nontraditional research outputs and OS activities assessment culture can slowly change towards a more responsible and OS aware RA.

Adoption of ORCID and obtaining PIDs for all kinds of research outputs as well as use of open licenses like [Creative Commons](#) CC0 or CC-BY is central for increasing findability and accessibility of research.

Preprints as evidence of scholarly and academic productivity are important. Sharing also unexpected and not so perfect results benefit the whole research community. Free and open platforms like [OSF](#), [arXiv](#) and [bioRxiv](#) support OS by providing platforms for publishing preprints.

A question is how open and free information systems and databases could be widely adopted and correspondingly how to give up using paid databases like Elsevier's Scopus or Clarivate's Web of Science.

For reflection

Questions for reflection to organizations and institutions:

- What OS declarations is the organization committed to?
- Is OS encouraged and incentivized by the organization in general and through assessment?
- How open is the institution in sharing OS information on their hiring policies?
- How to move from OS performance monitoring to impact monitoring?
- What are the biggest challenges for making OS as the new normal?
- Openness of the RA process?

Watch the DORA YouTube video on Balanced, broad, responsible: a practical guide for research evaluators in https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=q_NCE80xi

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